

Undervalued Yet Vital: A Comparative Review of Regulating Ecosystem Services Using IPBES and TEEB Frameworks in BR Hills, India

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Abstract

Ecosystem services (ES) are the benefits that people get from nature, with regulatory services like carbon sequestration, water management, pollination, and pest control playing an important part in sustaining human well-being. Despite their significance, these services often get neglected, especially in socio-ecological systems like the BR Hills in Western Ghats, where natural complexity combines with Indigenous community reliance. This study provides a comprehensive analysis of two worldwide frameworks—the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES) and The Economics of Ecosystems and Biodiversity (TEEB)—to assess their suitability for evaluating regulating services in the BR Hills. A comparative evaluation matrix was created using 51 selected papers, with seven criteria: inclusivity, precision, scalability, community relevance, coherence, resilience, and service definition. The results suggest that IPBES excels in inclusion and community relevance, incorporating Indigenous knowledge and cultural values, although it requires significant resources and has communication issues. TEEB allows for rapid, standardised economic assessments with high policy acceptance, but it is limited in its inclusion and sensitivity to socio-cultural factors. Both theories have shortcomings in addressing temporal dynamics, regional heterogeneity, and equity. To balance conservation

priorities and human well-being in the Western Ghats, a hybrid strategy is advocated that combines the inclusiveness of IPBES with the economic accuracy of TEEB.

Keywords: BR Hills, Western Ghats, Regulating Ecosystem Services, IPBES, TEEB, Valuation

Introduction

Ecosystem services (ES) are the diverse benefits people derive from nature (Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, 2005). Regulating ES such as Carbon sequestration, Water regulation, Pollination, etc. provide essential indirect support that strongly correlates with Human well-being (Balasubramanian, 2019; Guo et al., 2010; Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, 2005). Despite their vital role in society, regulating ES is often disregarded and underappreciated since it is not used directly or perceived by individuals (Villamagna et al., 2013). This becomes especially true in the context of BR Hills in the western ghats.

Figure: The BR Hills Region, Source- <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/rs70201619>.

The Biligiri Rangaswamy Temple Wildlife Sanctuary (BRTWLS) serves as a distinctive link between the Western Ghats and the Eastern Ghats in Karnataka, India (Balasubramanian, 2022). It is 574.8 km² in size and has an abundance of biodiversity. BRTWLS is situated between 600 and 1800 meters above sea level, with winter temperatures ranging from 9 to 16 °C and summer temperatures from 20 to 38 °C. Rainfall ranges from 600 mm in the lowlands to 3000 mm at higher elevations per year (Mallegowda et al., 2015). The sanctuary is also home to 12,500 Soligas, the tribal community, according to the 2011 Census (Chandramouli, C., & General, R., 2011). The region is extremely distinct due to the variation of altitude, temperature, and rainfall, supporting an abundance of organisms that are dispersed throughout an extensive variety of habitat types and the Indigenous community (Kammathy et al., 2024). The region thus generates a multitude of Regulating ES which are highly context and region specific that are often challenging to understand using the largescale view of various global frameworks available. The added relation of the tribal people with the forest fosters intricate association and complex valuation of the ES.

Problem statement

The absence of systematic, context specific valuation approach and the complex ecological setting, active Indigenous community and distinct socio-economic conditions provides unique challenges regarding management of Regulating ES.

Research Gap

The current research and frameworks overlook non - market Regulating ES and assess it weakly.

Proposed Solution

A comparative review of the leading frameworks IPBES and TEEB for their assessment and application in BR Hills, Western Ghats. Thus, providing a comprehensive and inclusive report for valuation of the regulating ES.

Background/Theoretical Framework

IPBES

Figure: The conceptual framework of IPBES. Source - <http://www.ipbes.net/conceptual-framework>

The Inter-governmental Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES) was formed in 2012, on the similar grounds of the Inter-governmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), (IPCC, 2006). The framework focuses on Nature's Contribution to People (NCP) and

Indigenous and Local Knowledge (ILK) to assess the values of ES through its conceptual framework (Díaz et al., 2015). By incorporating plural and Indigenous knowledge claims into its multidimensional assessments, IPBES hopes to further advance this conversation between diverse epistemic communities, building on the MEA's shortcomings and experience (Hill et al., 2019).

TEEB

The Economics of Ecosystems and Biodiversity (TEEB) was formed in 2010 during COP10 on Convention on Biological Diversity in Nagoya, Japan (Van der Ploeg et al., 2010). Their motto is “making nature visible”. Its fundamental goal is to integrate environmental services and biodiversity values into all levels of decision-making. By using a systematic approach to valuation, it seeks to accomplish this goal by assisting decision-makers in identifying the diverse range of benefits offered by ecosystems and biodiversity, proving their economic worth, and, when necessary, incorporating those values into decision-making (UNEP, 2010a). TEEB mainly focuses on the economic estimation of services and has set of methods that can be used for economic valuation of regulating ecosystem services such as Climate regulation, Water Regulation, Pollination, etc (UNEP, 2010a).

Aim:

To conduct a comparative review of IPBES and TEEB and evaluate their applicability on valuation of Regulating services of the socio-ecological region of BR Hills.

Objectives:

1. To conduct a comparative review of the IPBES and TEEB frameworks.
2. To construct a context-specific evaluation matrix to compare IPBES and TEEB in terms of their operational feasibility, inclusivity, and data requirements for regulating services in Indian ecosystems.
3. To assess their applicability in the context of BR Hills and similar Indian ecosystems.

Methods

1. Eligibility criteria

This study focused on the works being carried around the frameworks of classification and for valuation of Ecosystem services, and the rest were excluded. Those were further grouped into TEEB and IPBES.

2. Information sources

An extensive search was carried on the repositories of Google Scholar and Web of Science. Along with that, reports from the specific organisations of TEEB and IPBES were collected.

3. Search strategy

The search was carried out using the keywords “IPBES framework ecosystem services valuation”, “TEEB framework ecosystem services valuation”, “Ecosystem services framework comparison”, “IPBES TEEB framework comparison”, “Western ghats ecosystem services valuation”. It was followed by specific ES such as “carbon sequestration”, “water regulation”, “pollination” and “pest control”.

4. Selection process

The results were screened for the comparison of frameworks, their region of application and studies not focusing on India or western ghats were rejected. They were further scrutinised based on the types of ES and the frameworks they utilised.

5. Synthesis methods

The studies will be used to develop a comparison criterion on the seven categories. The criteria are defined as follows:

a. Inclusivity

This is based on the inclusiveness of the local and traditional knowledge systems along with global established criteria and using them for the valuation of ES. This also assesses the stakeholder engagement in the decision-making process so that it remains holistic.

b. Precision

This includes the technical data requirements, whether qualitative or quantitative, standardized methods available for assessment, etc. It also measures the ease of using the framework for assessments.

c. Scalability

This evaluates the application level of the frameworks, whether they are highly local, site specific or global, having broad spectrums of definitions and ES categories. Also, their flexibility in application of both scenarios.

d. Community relevance

This measures the potential utilisation of the assessment by the local community and how well it works for them in their setting for their needs.

e. Cohesive and Coherent

Cohesiveness and coherence demonstrate the extent to which a framework integrates concepts, methodologies, and values, facilitates interdisciplinary collaboration, and connects science with policy and practice.

f. Resilience

In valuation frameworks, resilience denotes the capacity of ecosystems to maintain or adjust their services under stress, driving adaptive management.

g. Ecosystem Services Definition and Classification

Ecosystem services definition and classification evaluate the clarity, structure, and interconnection of services, facilitating comparability, trade-off analysis, and efficient policy implementation.

The study will also focus on the potential utilisation of the frameworks for the valuation of regulating services, carbon sequestration, pollination, pest control and water regulation and will assess which of both is more suitable for what aspect of their assessment.

6. Risk of Bias

The bias that lies depends on the nature of the study selected. Since there are articles, research papers, interim reports and case studies, the selection criteria for each one overlaps each other and can be a potential risk of bias.

Prisma Flow Diagram

PRISMA 2020 flow diagram for updated systematic reviews which included searches of databases, registers and other sources

Results

In the primary stage of review, 68 studies were selected. They were divided into 47 journal articles and 21 reports. 4 of the articles were removed due to duplicity and ineligibility. They were further scrutinized for following the selected frameworks or valuation of decided ES and it produced 32 articles as the appropriate research. Out of the 21 reports, 3 were excluded due having generic scope and having non-specific ES, producing 19 reports as the final lot. Hence for this study we have 51 published literatures that are specified in the desired criteria.

Comparative Analysis Matrix

Framework →	IPBES	TEEB
Criterion ↓		
Inclusivity	High Relevance	Low Relevance
Scalability	Medium Relevance	Medium Relevance
Precision	Medium Relevance	High Relevance
Community Relevance	High Relevance	Low Relevance
Cohesive and Coherent	High Relevance	Medium Relevance
Resilience	Medium Relevance	Low Relevance
Ecosystem Services Definition and Classification	High Relevance	Medium Relevance

Legend: High Relevance Medium Relevance Low Relevance

The Comparison matrix reveals seven evaluation dimensions of distinct framework profiles. IPBES consistently exhibits medium-to-high performance across most dimensions, while TEEB exhibits high precision but significant deficiencies in inclusivity, resilience, and community relevance.

Scalability Assessment

IPBES displays excellent global scalability due to its intergovernmental framework, which allows for consistent implementation across local and national evaluations. Despite this, medium regional scalability requires significant customization for unique situations, as illustrated by difficulties integrating local knowledge systems successfully (Dunkley et al., 2018; Luque-Lora, 2024; Nijnik & Miller, 2017).

TEEB demonstrates excellent global scalability with common value databases, allowing for quick economic evaluations globally. Benefit transfer constraints restrict medium local scalability, which may fail to account for specific ecological and socioeconomic shifts (TEEB, 2010; Van der Ploeg et al., 2010).

Inclusivity Assessment

IPBES achieves high knowledge system inclusiveness via specific Indigenous Local Knowledge (ILK) integration and several evidence-based methodologies. High stakeholder participation is achieved via multi-stakeholder interface design, yet implementation issues persist (Christie et al., 2019; IPBES, 2022; Kenter, 2018).

TEEB has poor knowledge systems inclusiveness, with a focus on Western scientific methodologies and insufficient absorption of indigenous viewpoints. There is low stakeholder involvement via expert-led procedures, with little community participation (Obst, C. and Sharma, K., 2018).

Precision Assessment

IPBES has moderate methodological accuracy since it employs both qualitative and quantitative methodologies, as well as confidence level evaluations, which allow for the recognition of ambiguity. High data needs necessitate detailed evidence synthesis from several sources, including grey literature (IPBES, 2019).

TEEB provides high methodological accuracy due to standardized economic valuation procedures and a uniform database structure. High data needs, including a large worldwide database providing precise value estimates for ecological services (McVittie A. and Hussain S. S., 2013).

Community relevance

The IPBES scores in local context relevance is high due to a focus on context-specific viewpoints and the integration of local knowledge. Also has high cultural values inclusivity by acknowledging multiple worldviews, relational values, and instrumental values (Christie et al., 2019; IPBES, 2022; Luque-Lora, 2024)

The TEEB ranks low in local relevance, since standardized economic values don't always represent indigenous cultural and ecological circumstances. It also has low cultural values due inclusion based on monetary worth, which may overlook non-market cultural relevance (TEEB, 2009).

Cohesive and Coherent

IPBES scores high by providing a consistent NCP framework with cross-disciplinary potential and a robust internal logic. Nevertheless, the integration of natural and social disciplines continues to be a challenge, particularly in the context of holistic assessments in the Western Ghats (Bordt & Saner, 2018; Díaz et al., 2015).

TEEB performs moderately by offering a standardised, coherent economic framework that is characterised by plain definitions and robust internal consistency. Its focus guarantees effective coordination throughout the Western Ghats, even though its scope is restricted by the limited integration of ecological and social aspects (EIGENRAAM et al., 2020).

Resilience

Scoring moderately, IPBES offers systematic categorisation of services into material, non-material, and regulating categories. It also explicitly acknowledges service combinations, synergies, and trade-offs by employing a systems approach (Water, Land And Ecosystems (Wle), 2014).

TEEB guarantees consistent application by employing standardised service definitions with explicit operational categories. Yet scores low because it primarily handles services independently, with only a limited recognition of groups or trade-offs (EIGENRAAM et al., 2020).

Ecosystem Services Definition and Classification-

IPBES performs high by providing systematic categorisation across service types and clear NCP definitions. It also expressly considers ES groups, synergies, and trade-offs, thereby facilitating improved communication and integrated management among diverse stakeholders in the Western Ghats (Pascual et al., 2017).

TEEB offers standardised, unambiguous service definitions for consistent application, but it has limited recognition of Ecosystem services, concentrating on individual valuations hence scores moderate. This may restrict comprehension of interconnected systems, including agriculture, forest habitats, and pollination, in the Western Ghats (de Groot et al., 2020).

Application in Western Ghats for Regulating services-

Carbon Sequestration

Western ghats forest ecosystems trap around 37.5 million tons of carbon each year, which is worth Rs 100 billion (\$1.4 billion) at current carbon market rates. The Western ghats has 1.23 million gigagrams of carbon in plants and soils (Balasubramanian & Sangha, 2023; Kenter, 2018).

IPBES evaluates carbon services in storage, sequestration, and climate regulation, including local management and community viewpoints and managing uncertainty via confidence levels. TEEB's regional carbon database offers uniform monetary value (₹2,142/tonne), allowing for fast economic assessments and benefit transfer (Balasubramanian & Sangha, 2023).

Water Regulation

The Western Ghats act as the "water tower" of southern India, supporting 58 rivers and providing water availability for 245 million individuals. Forest cover has a direct impact on stream permanence, with more than 55% native vegetation providing permanent flows (Balasubramanian & Sangha, 2023; Dandekar, 2023; Ramachandra & Bharath, 2020).

The extensive IPBES framework examines water governance in the context of nature-society interactions. It pertains to local rivers and streams regarding water availability, utilizing Indigenous watershed management knowledge and the cultural significance of water bodies. TEEB assigns economic value to flood management, water purification, and supply regulation. It facilitates cost-benefit analysis of watershed enhancements by standardizing the values of water-related services (Díaz et al., 2015; Van der Ploeg et al., 2010).

Pollination

Western Ghats are essential for spice cultivation, since 39 out of 63 significant food plant species rely on bee pollination. The area sustains varied pollinator groups crucial for preserving agricultural output and the reproduction of wild flora (Ramachandra & Bharath, 2020; Ravindranath et al., 2016).

IPBES employs a systems approach to evaluate pollination by including agricultural information, crop-pollinator interactions, and landscape-level determinants influencing pollinator groups. TEEB employs direct economic assessment of pollination via crop production and market prices, utilising a database of predefined figures for agricultural systems to evaluate the monetary implications (Balachandra et al., 2014; Vohland & Nadim, 2015).

Pest Control

In the Western Ghats, coffee agroforests sustain varied groups of natural enemies, with ants contributing 34% of arthropod predatory services. Avian fauna and bats play a crucial role in pest management within agricultural environments (Bhaduri, 2012; Jithila & Prasad, 2018; Ramachandra & Bharath, 2020).

IPBES assesses pest management within the context of ecosystem functionality, including the habitat requirements of natural predators, agricultural methods, and Indigenous ecological wisdom. TEEB quantifies the economic benefits of pest management by assessing decreased pesticide expenditures and enhanced crop yields, using standard metrics that facilitate comparisons between biological and chemical methods for agricultural decision-making (IPBES et al., 2022; Ravindranath et al., 2016).

Discussion

Based on the analysis of the 51 research documents the study shows that both IPBES and TEEB show distinct strengths and limitations which can influence their applicability in various scenarios.

Valuation gaps and methodological limitations

Both models have methodological issues. Neither sufficiently represents temporal dynamics, especially the seasonal and inter-annual variations of monsoon-dependent services (Christie et al., 2019; EIGENRAAM et al., 2020). They also suffer in depicting spatial variation within micro-habitats and service linkages, where synergies and trade-offs (e.g., carbon storage vs. groundwater recharge) are often neglected (Chopra et al., 2022; Kenter, 2018). Gaps remain

in quantification methodologies tailored to tropical mountainous ecosystems, the incorporation of indigenous knowledge, and uncertainty evaluation, underscoring the need for context-specific instruments instead of uniform, generic applications (Kothandaraman et al., 2020; Pandeya et al., 2016).

Policy and Implementation Obstacles

At the policy level, both frameworks encounter a national-local disjunction, hindering the conversion of evaluations into implementable initiatives (Balasubramanian & Sangha, 2021). Lacking institutional capacity—especially at the state and district levels—further hinders implementation (George et al., 2025). Furthermore, neither framework sufficiently addresses the allocation of gains and costs across social groups, creating disparities about equality in conservation and development results (Harini et al., 2025).

Applicability of IPBES and TEEB

IPBES excels in scenarios necessitating multi-stakeholder involvement, the integration of varied information, and an awareness of cultural values (Luque-Lora, 2024). Its participatory methodology promotes legitimacy and inclusivity, effective in socio-ecologically complex areas such as the Western Ghats (IPBES et al., 2022). Although, IPBES demands extensive, resource-intensive procedures, and its intricate results may complicate communication with policymakers (IPBES et al., 2022; Vohland & Nadim, 2015).

TEEB, conversely, is designed for swift evaluations and communicates in the economic terms that appeals to politicians, entrepreneurs, and investors (EIGENRAAM et al., 2020).

Standardized valuation systems enable comparison across locations and promote business-oriented conservation initiatives (TEEB, 2009; Van der Ploeg et al., 2010).

However, its economically focused framing may seem culturally insensitive, overlooking non-use or regulating services, and often neglects equality issues in the distribution of benefits (TEEB, 2009).

Conclusion

The IPBES and TEEB frameworks provide useful but different methodologies for the valuing of ecosystem services in the Western Ghats. IPBES ensures inclusion and community significance vital for policy formulation in this culturally rich biodiversity hotspot, while TEEB delivers accuracy and economic transparency required for swift decision-making and investment validation. The selection of frameworks needs to be determined by decision

settings, resources available, and stakeholder requirements, rather than assuming universal application.

Gaps exist in both frameworks concerning temporal dynamics, regional heterogeneity, and the integration of various knowledge systems. Future development must emphasize hybrid methodologies that integrate the economic accuracy of TEEB with the inclusiveness and contextual awareness of IPBES.

The intricate socio-ecological systems, cultural variety, and essential ecosystem services of the Western Ghats and specifically BR Hills, need strategies that balance economic efficiency with social equity. Neither approach alone includes this complexity, underscoring the need for ongoing innovation in ecosystem service assessment techniques that more effectively address both conservation objectives and human well-being in globally significant biodiversity hotspots.

Future Directions

This review is limited to a set of criteria and regulating services. The amount of related journal articles, and reports are limited as well. It is highly likely that the broader literature has some additional information to expand the criteria of this review. The exclusion of Scopus as a repository also limits the scope of the review. Furthermore, assessments on the regulating services applicability, specifically pest control, was based on specific judgement of how it can be accounted for, using the overlying context of other services and outputs.

The future work suggestions include framing and adoption of a hybrid application strategy where TEEB can be used for quick and standardized economic screening followed by IPBES for participatory engagement and prioritization with context-specific planning. This ensures both monetary and non-monetary values are included.

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